

An Examination of Some Basic Dyes as to their Suitability for Preparing Acid-sensitive Dye Reagents in Benzene

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Acid-sensitive dye reagents in benzene have been prepared from a large number of basic dyes by quick extraction of their aqueous alkaline solutions with benzene. Acids in benzene solution change the colour of these dye reagents in benzene. The acid-sensitivity of the respective dye reagents has been examined colorimetrically with the use of dilute (10^{-3} to 10^{-4} *N*) benzene solutions of stearic acid.

Partially *N*-alkylated dyes of the rhodamine and methyl violet classes have been found to produce deeply coloured reagents of high acid-sensitivity, detecting as low as 10^{-6} *N* stearic acid. Fully alkylated or unalkylated dyes have been found to be insensitive or less sensitive in general.

The acid-sensitive dye reagents have been found to be almost equally sensitive to benzene-soluble salts; aliphatic amines in fairly low concentration can be detected by them, the limit of identification with diethylamine having been found to be about 10^{-4} *N*.

A new dye technique, called the "Dye interaction technique", recently developed in our laboratory, has lately been employed for the quantitative determination² of acids, bases, and salts in the near-micronormal concentration range.

Acid dyes, particularly the halogenated phthaleins, when extracted with benzene from their aqueous solution (*pH* 3-5), yield highly sensitive organo-extracts for the detection of traces of bases. Similarly some basic dyes under proper conditions yield acid-sensitive reagents in benzene. Suitability of acid dyes for detection of a base has been carefully examined and the sensitivity of some reagents, obtained from halogenated phthaleins, such as Eosin saure L neu, Eosin G etc., is so high² (detecting one thousandth of a microgram of diethylamine) as to leave little scope to investigate other dyes for the purpose.

Of the basic dyes, Calcozine rhodamine 6 Gx conc. has yielded an acid-sensitive dye reagent, which has been extensively used in our laboratory for routine detection and estimation of acids in the 10^{-3} to 10^{-6} *N* concentration range in benzene. The behaviour of the reagent is rather variable with slight changes in the method of preparation. Apparently there is much scope for improvement of this type of dye reagent. The present communication reports the results of screening a large number of basic dyes for such purposes.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure for the Preparation of the Dye Reagent.—The dye (4-5 mg.) in aqueous solution of the right *pH* range was extracted immediately with pure benzene (100 ml).

1. Palit, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 1531; *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 1441.
2. Palit and Ghosh, *Microchem. Tech.*, Symposium series, 1961, 2, 663.

With the exception of the violet triphenylmethane dyes (viz., the methyl violets and Gentian violet), a phosphate buffer of pH 10.0 was used during extraction. The extraction of the violet dyes for the preparation of acid-sensitive reagents was carried out in strongly alkaline aqueous solution. Generally 5-10 mg. of a violet dye was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and the aqueous solution was then made strongly alkaline by adding a few pellets of sodium hydroxide whereby the hydroxide of the dye base was deposited. The precipitated dye was immediately extracted with benzene (100 ml). Extraction of the violet dyes from strongly alkaline solution is necessary because the colour of the benzene extracts, which is yellow in general, is fairly stable only under such conditions. Extraction of the acid-sensitive violet dyes with an aqueous solution of pH 10 yielded brown or red-brown extracts, which were unstable and rapidly changed to the colorless and insensitive forms of the respective species.

It has been often noticed that if the solution of a basic dye in an alkaline buffer is kept for some time and then extracted with benzene, the dye reagent obtained is less sensitive to acids. The probable reason for this is that the buffer tends to convert a portion of the dye to the inactive carbinol base and this is minimised by dissolving the dye in the least volume of water, adding the requisite volume of benzene, finally adding the buffer, and quickly carrying out the extraction.

Procedure for Analysis.—The benzene extracts of the basic dyes, commonly called the dye reagents, are generally well preserved if kept over a few pellets of sodium hydroxide in dark at the room temperature (25-20°). To test the effect of acids on these dye reagents, equal volumes of benzene solution of an acid of known concentration and a dye reagent were mixed and any change in the colour of the dye reagent, due to the acid present, was noted. For the quantitative purpose, the colour changes were measured in a Hilger Spekker absorptiometer. A blank experiment must be run side by side for each reagent so as to be sure of any chance impurity and for the use as the reference liquid in the absorptiometer.

Acid-sensitivity of the Basic Dyes.—Some typical results, using benzene solution of stearic acid and benzene extracts of quite a number of basic dyes, are recorded in Table I. The suitable pH for extraction of the acid-sensitive dye reagents, the colour changes of the respective dye reagents with an acid, and the optical density values obtained in a 1-cm cell from millinormal to micronormal concentrations of the acid as measures of the depth of the colour produced at very low concentration of stearic acid are presented in appropriate columns of the table.

TABLE I

Acid-sensitivity of basic dyes.
(Stearic acid used as the acid)

*Dye.	Colour change.	Sensitivity limit.	†Optical density at stearic acid conc. of			
			10 ⁻³ N.	10 ⁻⁴ N.	10 ⁻⁵ N.	10 ⁻⁶ N.
1. Calcozine rhodamine 6Gx conc.	Orango-yellow to pink	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶ N	0.427	0.200	0.035	0.006
2. Rhodamine 6G extra methyl ester	„	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.342	0.135	0.005	0.002
3. Rhodamine 6G extra ethyl ester	„	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁵	0.360	0.150	0.020	0.004
4. Rhodamine 4G extra	„	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁵	0.320	0.130	0.020	0.009
5. Rhodamine 3GO	**Orange-yellow to pink fluorescent	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.380	0.243	0.040	0.010
6. Calcozine rhodamine BX	Colorless to pink	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁵	0.008	..	..	..
7. Rhodamine 3B extra	Faint pink to deeper pink	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁵	0.003	..	..	..
8. Rhodamine B base extract	Colorless insensitive	..	..	..	..	..
9. Calcozine new-fuch sine	Bright greenish yellow to pink	10 ⁻⁴ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.165	0.040	0.015	0.001
10. Pyronin	Orange-yellow to pink	10 ⁻⁴ to 10 ⁻⁵	0.353	0.142	0.012	..
11. Auramine O	Colorless to greenish yellow	10 ⁻³ to 10 ⁻⁴	0.030	0.010	..	..
12. Auramine OS	„	10 ⁻³ to 10 ⁻⁴	0.032	0.020	..	..
13. Nigrosine base	Brownish pink to violet-blue	10 ⁻³ to 10 ⁻⁴	0.061	0.030	0.001	..
14. Neutral red	Greenish yellow to pink-red	10 ⁻³	0.000	..	..	..
15. Methyl violet 3B	Brown-yellow to violet	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.387	0.246	0.070	0.030
16. Methyl violet 6B	(Colorless) light yellow to violet	10 ⁻³ to 10 ⁻⁵	0.080	0.050	0.010	..
17. Methyl violet N	Yellow to violet	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.310	0.190	0.032	0.010
18. Methyl violet extra H/conc.	Yellow to violet	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.190	0.106	0.029	0.015
19. Gentian violet	Yellow to violet	10 ⁻⁵ to 10 ⁻⁶	0.213	0.120	0.057	0.020
20. Crystal violet	Colorless (light violet) insensitive extract	..	..	..	..	..
21. Rosaniline base	Colorless (pale yellow) insensitive extract	..	..	..	..	..

*The violet dyes were extracted from strongly alkaline aqueous solutions; all other dyes were extracted from their aqueous solutions of pH 10.

†O.D. measurements with rhodamines, fuch sine, pyronin, and neutral red were carried out at 520 m μ , with violet dyes and nigrosine base at 575 m μ , and with auramines at 430 m μ in a Spekker absorptiometer.

**The orange-yellow colour of benzene extract of the rhodamine 3GO gradually changes to deep pink-violet with strong fluorescence.

DISCUSSION

Some rhodamines and violet dyes have been found to be able to detect as low as micromolar concentration of stearic acid, whereas some of the same classes of dyes are not at all sensitive. Among the rhodamines, rhodamine G class has been found to be

highly satisfactory, producing orange-yellow reagents, which change to pink on addition of a dilute solution of an acid. The acid-developed colour is stable for a long period and colorimetric measurements can be easily carried out. Rhodamine 3GO reagent, when freshly prepared, is also similarly sensitive, but it does not keep well and changes its colour from orange-yellow to fluorescent pink-violet and finally becomes insensitive to acid detection. Dyes of the rhodamine B class are found useless for the purpose. The insensitive rhodamine B dyes are fully alkylated, whereas sensitive dyes of the rhodamine G class are only partially alkylated. Complete alkylation therefore materially impairs the sensitivity. This is explained from structural consideration as follows.

During benzene extraction of a basic dye from its alkaline solution, the hydroxide base of the dye formed in the aqueous phase, being more soluble in benzene, passes almost completely to the benzene layer. Preservation over solid caustic soda facilitates formation of the anhydro-base by dehydration under suitable cases and thus the possibility of formation of carbinol base is checked. Formation of the anhydro-base is only possible if the dye is partially alkylated; fully alkylated dyes are constitutionally incapable of forming the anhydro-base. The hydroxide bases derived from the fully alkylated dyes are very strong; so they have the colour of the ionic form and tend to change readily into the respective carbinol bases. Less sensitive or insensitive dyes generally yield pale or colorless reagents and the most sensitive provide generally deeply coloured reagents, which under certain conditions gradually become colorless on keeping and thereby become less sensitive or insensitive. The colorless forms of the dyes in benzene are supposed to be the respective carbinol bases and their general insensitivity is ascribed to their weak and slow reactivity.

Like the rhodamine dyes, violet triphenylmethane dyes also conform more or less to the above pattern. Partially alkylated dyes, such as methyl violet 3B, methyl violet extra, Gentian violet, methyl violet N, etc., yield sensitive reagents and can detect micro-normal concentrations of stearic acid. Fully alkylated dye, e.g., crystal violet, however, yields an insensitive reagent. Acids change the yellow colour of the sensitive violet dye reagents to violet. The acid-developed violet colour is, however, not very stable and fades quite rapidly, the dye ultimately becoming colorless. For all qualitative purposes, the sensitive violet dyes are highly suitable because of the easy detection of the colour change from yellow to violet; but due to instability of the acid-developed violet colour, these are less suitable for quantitative purposes.

Next to the sensitive rhodamine and violet dyes in the order of acid-sensitivity are new-fuchsine and pyronin, the limit of stearic acid detection being 10^{-4} to 10^{-6} *N* for new-fuchsine and 10^{-4} to 10^{-5} *N* for pyronin. Auramines and neutral red yield insensitive reagents; nigrosine base yields a brownish pink reagent, which is also not very sensitive. The limit of stearic acid detection for these dyes is of the order of 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} *N*. Rosaniline base, having none of its NH_2 groups alkylated, is a fairly weak base and yields a pale yellow benzene extract of very poor acid-sensitivity.

For qualitative detection of benzene-soluble acids in near micronormal to micronormal range of concentrations, basic dyes of the rhodamine and methyl violet classes, which are only partially *N*-alkylated, are recommended. For quantitative purposes, rhodamine 6G dyes are particularly suitable because of the following advantages: (1) The reagents are fairly stable and easily preserved for months together. (2) The acid-developed colour

is also fairly stable and this suits colorimetric measurements. Due to the unstable nature of the acid-developed colour of the violet dye reagents, these are not very suitable for quantitative purposes. The suitability of rhodamine 6Gx conc. for the determination of acids in benzene has been reported in a previous communication².

Salt-sensitivity of the Basic Dyes.—The acid-sensitive dye reagents have also been found to be almost equally sensitive to benzene-soluble salts³, e.g., mercuric chloride and the quaternary ammonium and pyridinium halides dissolved in benzene. Almost micro-normal concentrations of these salts have been easily detected with the most acid-sensitive dye reagents, such as rhodamine 6G reagents and methyl violet 3B or gentian violet reagent. Since various other inorganic and organic salts are insoluble or difficultly soluble in benzene and the solubilities are difficult to determine, a systematic determination of salts; with the help of the dye reagents has not been possible. Benzene extracts of some salts, such as KI, KCNS, etc. (pure form), ordinarily insoluble in benzene, produce faint changes in the colour of the acid-sensitive dye reagents, whereas others, such as NaCl, Na₂SO₄ etc., when similarly examined, produce no change. This behaviour of salts may be utilised to ascertain their solubilities in traces in benzene, at least on a qualitative basis. The acid-sensitive dye reagents have been widely employed in our laboratory for the detection and estimation of a large variety of anionic groups or end group in polymers, soluble in benzene³⁻⁴. Anionic groups present in benzene-insoluble polymers have also been detected by this technique. The insoluble polymers bearing the anionic groups are easily stained by the sensitive dye reagents, but those having no anionic group remain practically stain-free. These observations foreshadow the possible determination of suitable functional groups in substances, insoluble in benzene, with the help of this dye technique.

Base-sensitivity of the Basic Dyes.—More interesting is the fact that organic bases, such as the aliphatic amines, are also detectable at fairly low concentrations with the help of the sensitive basic dye reagents. The change in colour of the respective dye reagents is generally the same, irrespective of whether it is brought about by acids, bases or salts.

TABLE II

Base-sensitivity of basic dyes.
(Diethylamine, DEA, used as the base)

Dye.	Colour change.	Sensitivity limit.	Optical density at DEA concentration of			
			10 ⁻² N.	10 ⁻³ N.	10 ⁻⁴ N.	10 ⁻⁵ N.
Calcozine rhodamine 6Gx conc.	Orange-yellow to pink	10 ⁻⁴ N	0.10	0.07	0.01	0.00
Methyl violet 3B	Yellow to violet	10 ⁻⁴	0.14	0.08	0.02	0.00

The sensitivity toward base detection with the sensitive basic dye reagents is not as high as with acid detection. 10⁻⁴ N-Diethylamine (DEA) is the limit to be detected by,

3. Palit and Ghosh, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1962, **58**, 1225.

4. Ghosh *et al.*, unpublished.

say, rhodamine 6Gx or methyl violet 3B. A sensitive acid dye reagent, viz., eosin saure L neu, however, can detect as low as $10^{-7}N$ solution of the same amine². The optical density values, using $10^{-2}N$ to $10^{-3}N$ benzene solutions of diethylamine with rhodamine 6Gx and methyl violet 3B reagents, are recorded in Table II, the results being obtained in a Spekker absorptiometer against the blank dye reagent as the reference liquid with the use of 1 cm cells.

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